

THE ROLE OF PRONUNCIATION IN TEACHING FOREIGN
LANGUAGES IN NON-PHILOLOGICAL INSTITUTIONS**Siddikova Nasiba**

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It is obvious that in the 21st century, the trend of globalization is leading to closer relationships between countries. Of all the different languages, English, as a global/international language (EGL/EIL) or a Lingua Franca (ELF) is widely used in communication between people and countries. The English language has spread and developed globally, which is a fact that cannot be ignored. As the main foreign language taught and employed in communication with foreigners, the use of English has dramatically increased in Uzbekistan. The decree of the president of the republic of Uzbekistan on measures for further enhancement of the system of teaching of foreign languages (Tashkent, December 10, 2012) enlarges our possibilities to introduce and implement the advanced foreign language teaching methods with the use modern and information - communication technologies.

As English teachers, we are always on the lookout for new and interesting ways to stimulate our language learners. The basic teaching is needed. Teaching the alphabets and the formation of the words is essential and a must. However, something is even more important.

Since English is the official language of this world it is of utmost importance that this language has to be taught in such a way that it will help us not just to speak and write and listen but to communicate. That is the Innovative Methods of Teaching English Language purpose of the language and that is what it must be used for. Hence, innovative methods help in bringing a change and most of the times for the better. It helps the students learn faster and in an efficient, interesting and an interactive manner and it is the teacher's responsibility to leave the traditional methods and make way for new and better methods for the students benefit.

Currently there is no consensus on how best to teach pronunciation in a classroom setting. But sometimes there appeared one question ***Do we need to teach pronunciation?*** As **Helen Fraser** (Senior Lecturer in Linguistics, University of New England, Armidale, NSW) mentioned that the pendulum has swung back again, and most ESL teachers now agree that explicit pronunciation teaching is an essential part of language courses. On the one hand, confidence with pronunciation allows learners the interaction with native speakers that is

so essential for all aspects of their linguistic development. On the other hand, poor pronunciation can mask otherwise good language skills, condemning learners to less than their deserved social, academic and work advancement.

What teaching models have influenced current teaching practice? For as long as people have been learning and teaching languages, there has been continual debate about how to describe the process and what the best ways of doing it are. Much current teaching practice is the direct result of such constructive argument. There have been some traditional language learning techniques that have been used for many years. In more recent times, there have been five teaching models, which have had a strong influence on classroom practice- and which teachers and trainers still refer to. They are grammar-translation, audio-lingualism, Total physical response, task-based learning and communicative language teaching. What does language study consist of? Whatever the level of the students and however language study is organized within teaching sequences, there are four things that students need to do with new language: be exposed to it, understand its meaning, understand its form, how it is constructed and practice it.

Pronunciation is one of the aspects of effective communication. Learning to pronounce words correctly is an important skill because it helps to build the foundation for child's future education.

Historically, spelling approaches have been broadly classified as "child-centered" or "instruction-centered" but in recent times teachers have tended to combine elements of these theoretically different perspectives to design new approaches. At the same time, all teachers reported a commitment to spelling practices aligned with an instruction-centered approach including separate spelling lessons each morning of at least 20 minutes in duration and weekly or fortnightly pretest-learn-test cycles of word lists.

Word study is an approach to spelling instruction that moves away from a focus on memorization. The approach reflects what researchers have discovered about the alphabetic, pattern, and meaning layers of English orthography.

Teachers use a variety of hands-on activities, often called word work, to help students actively explore these layers of information. When studying the alphabetic layer, students examine the relationship between letters and sounds. They learn to match single letters and pairs of letters (e.g., *ch*) to specific sounds and, in doing so, to create words. When students study the pattern layer, they look beyond single or paired letter-sounds to search for larger patterns that guide the grouping of letters (e.g., *CVCe*). Studying the meaning layer helps

students to understand how the English spelling system can directly reflect the semantic relationships across related words. For example, students come to understand that the second vowel in *composition* is spelled with an *o* because it is related to *compose*.

Students learn word knowledge that they can apply generally to a wide range of reading and writing activities. Of course, students learn to spell a great many words through word study lessons and daily word work activities, but the instruction is more conceptual than that of traditional spelling programs. This is important because what students remember about specific words are related to what they know about English spelling in general (Ehri, 1992). Focus your word study lessons on the very English words work, so that students will form useful generalizations, they can apply to words they want to read or spell.

It is important for teachers to realize that they do not 'teach' spelling as such, but rather equip the learner with a number of strategies they can use to help them with their spelling. Many students believe that English spelling has no structure. However, it is important to point out to learners that many words do follow a pattern.

Most of all, it is essential to approach spelling in the context of the student's needs. We remember things that interest us most and are relevant to our lives.

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